

Bureaucratic Corruption on Devolved Units on Hard – Core Infrastructural Service Delivery; Case of Lake Region Economic Block, Kenya

Author's Details:

¹**Fred Omweri Siambe**, PhD Candidate of Public Policy, Kenyatta University; Part – Time Lecturer; Department of Political Science and Peace Studies - Kisii University, Kisii, Kenya.

^{2*}**Dr. Thomas Otieno Juma**, PhD; Lecturer of Public Administration; Department of Humanities and Social Sciences - University of Kabianga; Kericho, Kenya.

Abstract

The interest in devolving government services arose from the bottlenecks posed by hitherto centralized governments where bureaucracy among regime holders became in excess to undo its merits in service delivery but to a greater extent evolving into bureaucratic corruption on premium projects – infrastructure. This paper asks whether infrastructural service delivery will suffice in the bigger Lake Region Economic Block (LREB) when cases of corruption have been repeatedly associated to the devolved units as they are now. The study was aided by three objectives centering on the nature, the extent, and correlation of bureaucratic corruption to hard – core infrastructural service delivery in the LREB. Using a qualitative study from a cross section of decentralized systems, the study found out that indeed among devolved units, bureaucratic corruption (BC) exist and it takes different forms spreading through the structure of devolved units and much to this there is a general marked correlation to premium projects. On this basis, generalization can be made that the on progress Lake Region Economic Block, Kenya if not properly provided with checks and balances from the onset, could enhance BC than benefit citizens economically as a block.

Keywords: *Bureaucracy/ Bureaucratic Corruption/ Corruption/ Devolved Units/ Hardcore Infrastructure/ Service Delivery/ LREB*

Introduction and Conceptualization

The effort to enhance infrastructural service delivery in counties is one of the important functions of the county governments in Kenya (COK, 2010). In spite of this, bureaucratic corruption (BC) seems to find its way in the devolved units (Wabukala, 2018). On the contrary, there is a marked absence of studies that interrogate corruption within the system of bureaucracy towards hard- core infrastructural service delivery so as to provide solutions to such corruption. According to Mbaku (2008), corruption remains an obstacle to economic development.

In Mbaku's assertion, he highlights corruption as an ill to development but again according to this study, corruption being an obstacle can be an indicator to existence of bureaucratic corruption even though he doesn't out rightly point it out. Bureaucrats (Apter, 1963) are believed to exploit their public positions to generate benefits for themselves rather than for the common good of the country and citizens as a whole. In as much as Apter suggests that bureaucrats are inherently elite, which is true, morally and dutifully again, bureaucrats acting in ideal situations should be very helpful to the delivery of public services and management of public goods/assets.

Source: *Authors, 2020*

In the conceptualization, we come to understand that infrastructure can exist in various perspectives; One being soft infrastructure involving human capital and the supportive institutions and system frameworks that enhance this kind of infrastructure. Secondly, in reference to the title above and most commonly the preoccupation of many actors' interests in the devolved units in Kenya is the - hard infrastructure (the 'lucrative' infrastructure) comprising the physical component of housing, roads, bridges, among others.

For hard – core infrastructural service delivery to be attained and achieved as to the following normal standards and parameters of; Quality/Productivity, Timely, Cost/Budget, Efficiency, Effectiveness, Accessibility, and Equity, it depends on the lack of or presence of bureaucratic corruption. Suggested in the framework here is that the presence of bureaucratic corruption without hypothesizing alters greatly the outcome of hard – core infrastructure service delivery, under the existing interventions.

Statement of the Problem

The inception of decentralization in Kenya through devolved units has been praised as a milestone (World Bank, 2012) through which services hitherto delayed by the central government from reaching the grassroots equitably could now be attained. Among the devolved services in the current Kenyan political dispensation are the infrastructural services whose delivery stands critical in the practice of decentralization. An efficient, responsible, transparent, and accountable bureaucracy within public administration is of paramount importance for proper functioning and delivery of infrastructural service delivery in counties. In spite of efforts to enhance

infrastructural service delivery in counties, bureaucratic corruption seems to find its way in the county public service. According to Sohail and Cavill (2006), there has been an increase in international concern about the extent of corruption in the construction industry. For example the American Society of Civil Engineers claims that corruption accounts for an estimated \$340 billion of worldwide construction costs each year. According to EACC (2018) citizens give bribes because it is the only way to get government services; and it is the only way to hasten public services. Surprisingly, EACC report affirms that 76 per cent of Kenyans do not receive government services after failing to pay a bribe. According to EACC (2017) the survey conducted in 39 counties exposed rampant corruption owing to lack of transparency in service deliver. Corruption is most prevalent in infrastructural services delivery such as roads ,housing , water and other infrastructure construction .The report further says corruption in the in infrastructure departments is manifested in bribery, abuse of office, conflict of interest, nepotism, favoritism, absenteeism, embezzlement, kickbacks, fraud and procurement irregularities. Corruption in construction projects undermines the benefits of infrastructure. In as much as some studies attempt to interrogate corruption in construction industry, many studies have somehow not delved into this area of research. It is worth noting that studies have looked at corruption in soft-core infrastructure which pertains to the provision of services such as healthcare, education, security, forms of governance, transparency, accountability and human and property rights. There is a marked absence of studies that interrogate corruption within the system of bureaucracy as to do with hard-core infrastructural service delivery, which pertains to the physical structures which comprises road networks, railway lines, airports, water supply, housing, telecommunication, power, transportation and sewage lines, which this study would wish to call bureaucratic corruption. From the foregoing, there is a clear gap that this study intends to fill and much more in relation to Lake Region Economic Block (LREB). This will provide a basis of making inference to finding solution to bureaucratic corruption (BC) among the emerging county regional blocks in Kenya.

The Lake Region Economic Block (LREB)

Lake Region Economic Block is a group of thirteen counties curved from Nyanza, Western and some parts of Rift valley in Kenya. The counties in this block include: Bungoma, Kakamega, Trans-Nzoia, Busia, Vihiga, Kisii, Nyamira, Kericho Bomet Migori, Homabay, Siaya, and Kisumu (Deloitte,2018). Lake Region Economic Block seems to be a progressive group of counties currently in Kenya. Despite this, according to corruption index, EACC Report (2016), EACC Report (2017) and EACC Report (2018) among the highest ranking counties with corruption cases include: Nyamira, Kisii, Homabay, Bomet, Trans-Nzoia, Busia and Kakamega. Likewise among the least (minimal) corrupt cases, Kericho features among others. This mix makes LREB an interesting case study for interrogation.

Justification and Significance

This paper is beneficial to a number of organizations and scholars alike. To the scholars, it will add nuance to academic rigour and on the other hand, it will be a reference trigger for more studies. For the individual county governments, it will show effects of BC and relation to hard core infrastructural service delivery which again to the emerging Lake Region Economic Block (LREB), the study will be essential in harnessing the overall goal of efficient, accountable, and responsive group of counties towards the national goals of devolution including self-bureaucratic reforms. The national government actors will find it imperative since it will be a source of information on bureaucratic corruption whereas to the service providers, the study is important as it will inform on the element of cost of corruption which cascades through essential services to affect the government, the providers, and the citizens at large in economic and social terms. Finally to the government financiers, the study opens a rethink on mechanisms of dealing with corruption and corrupt regimes/governments knowing that it is a loss to their investment.

The Nature of Bureaucratic Corruption on Devolved Units on Infrastructural Service Delivery

The emergence of county governance in Africa and the Kenyan case in particular had central citizenry quest behind their push. As is highlighted herein, (D'Arcy and Cornell, 2016) avers that decentralization is often

proposed as a potential solution to the problems facing African states. As extreme centralization is seen to undermine democracy and development, and enable debilitating forms of politics like rent seeking and ethnic patronage, decentralization is suggested as the necessary corrective. Decentralization is also advocated as a way to protect minorities, diffuse conflict, boost local development, and bring politics within the people's reach. For these reasons, since the 1980s decentralization has been supported by donors as an institutional fix for the problems of African states and has been implemented in a majority of countries.

Indeed as Asea (2018) puts it, the existence of government is to deliver social services that will make people's lives meaningful and worth living. To achieve this cardinal role of government, local governments as a tier of government were created to bring government closer to the people at the rural communities and for transformation of lives at that lowest level. One of the ways of realizing government closer to the people at the grassroots is through the delivery of social services in a satisfactory, timely, effective and adequate manner.

Many hope Kenya, which introduced devolution in the 2010 constitution and voted for the first time for the devolved governments in March 2013, will not be an exception. The devolution of political, fiscal, and administrative powers to 47 counties has been presented as the solution to the underlying pathologies of Kenyan politics. The issue of development is directly associated with services offered to the public including; health, electricity, water, housing, and road infrastructures (Bagaka, undated). Bagaka further emphasizes that a downward accountability mechanism where people-elected, nominated or appointed officials run local affairs of the devolved governments and are accountable to those who elect them. Bagaka's argument confirms what the principal-agent theory stands for that the citizens should be the center of public service delivery. As much as this is ideal, however, bureaucracy has bled to bureaucratic corruption which has been a stapling broke to the realization of devolved goals and objectives (World Bank, 2005).

Hard –core Infrastructural service delivery is critical in socio-economic development in society. Uchechi, Peter & Lionel (2014) points out that while some economists associate infrastructure with economic and social overhead capital, which includes facilities such as power, transport and communications, others see it as embracing social overhead which includes facilities for water supplies, education, health, information, town and country planning and social welfare. According to Oshikoya et al (1999), Ubi et al (2011), the definition of infrastructure falls into two complementary categories, namely: social or soft-core infrastructure and physical or hard-core infrastructure. Soft-core infrastructure pertains to the provision of healthcare and education, type of governance, transparency/accountability and property right and is often viewed as the driving force for economic activity. On the other hand, hard-core infrastructure pertains to physical structures and comprises telecommunication, power, transportation, water supply and sewage. They are generally viewed as the wheels of economic activity. Infrastructure; be soft-core or otherwise, provides the basic foundation on which the take-off into self-sustaining growth is not only possible but is also assured and cumulative (Jhingan, 2003).

Leys (1965) refers to corruption as behavior that breaks some rule, written or unwritten, about the proper purpose to which a public office/institution has been put. Werner (1983) suggests three further types of definition: (a) Public-office-centered definitions which involve a deviation from legal and public duty norms for private benefit, whether in the form of pecuniary, status or influence gains. (b) Market-centered definitions viewing corruption as a maximizing activity in which officials manipulate pecuniary gains according to the supply and demand in the market place of their official domains. (c) Public-interest-centered definitions stressing the betrayal of public interest by preferring particular to common interests.

As much as the above definitions does not specifically define what bureaucratic corruption, aspects raised in these definitions encompass the role of bureaucrats especially in the delivery of hard -core infrastructural services. In the infrastructural sector there are specific rules that have to be observed by the bureaucrat (Public officer) for proper functioning failure to observe them culminates to bureaucratic corruption as implied in Leys'

definition. Delivery of hard-core infrastructural services can be done by the government or through private sector commonly referred to as public private partnership (PPP) but the government still specifies the quantity and quality of services it requires from the private sector (OECD,2008). As Cavill & Sohail (2007) puts it these services (hard-core infrastructural services) are normally the responsibility of a local government or central government, but may be provided by the private sector .In public private partnership, the government in most cases avail the funds and awards the works to the private partners to implement the project under the supervision of the government. On this basis, Werner's definition is applicable to his study. Werner definition summarizes corruption into public-centered, market- centered and public interest- centered. Werner's forms of corruption emerge when the county governments fund or give tenders to private sector to implement hard-core infrastructural services. In this scenario, the cost of projects can be infuriated, self-interests might override the public interest since it is at the discretion of the bureaucrats to provide bill of quantities of every infrastructural project hence encouraging bureaucratic corruption. Klitgaard (1988) sums up that corruption occurs when an agent betrays the principal's interest in pursuit of one's own. Further to this bureaucratic corruption refers to the corrupt acts of the bureaucrats in dealings with either superiors or with the public (Shrabani, 2009). In most of the cases, the public may be required to bribe bureaucrats either to receive a service to which they are entitled or to speed up a bureaucratic procedure (Kaufman, 1997).In some cases, bureaucratic corruption may even influence provision of service that is not supposed to be available (Bardhan,1997).

According to Shrabani (2009) bureaucratic corruption takes variety of forms and exists at various levels within the bureaucracy. For instance, Shrabani points out that corrupt bureaucrat exploit their powers to extract bribes while carrying out tasks assigned to them by their superior-the political elite. He further adds that there are different variations of bribes that constitute bureaucratic corruption: bribes that equate to demand and supply, bribes as incentive payments for bureaucrats and bribes that lower costs. In examining Shrabani argument above, it is clear then with this type of operation in the bureaucracy especially in provision of hard –core infrastructural services; quality of service, efficiency, equity in service distribution, accessibility of services and cost of service will highly be compromised and the principal will automatically loss to attain the expected outcomes.

According to Mishra (2006) corruption conducted by public officials, represent a violation of procedures, either by making it look like as if all rules have been respected (through bid rigging or violation of communication rules, for instance), or by misusing legitimate deviations from the rules (for instance by referring to discretionary decisions, extraordinary circumstances or previous experience). The opportunities for such corruption depend on the number and/or nature of procedures. Such complexity can either enforce integrity or increase corruption (Moody-Stuart, 1997).This means for bureaucratic corruption to occur there must be collaboration or networking within the bureaucracy; implying that collaboration can be among the bureaucrats, who are agents or between the agent and the principal. Further, political levels can form part of the network which influences bureaucratic procedures, for instance by giving instructions to regulatory bodies on how to prioritize between tender criteria or factors that appear to support a political goal. This type of adds up to another form of bureaucratic corruption: misuse of power in order to get favors at the expense of public service delivery.

In support, Kempe (2015) opines that bureaucratic corruption as the utilization of bureaucratic official positions for private gain. It is the corruption by officials in public offices who are not vocationally politicians but who are aided and abetted by corrupt politicians and a corrupt political system. He states further that bureaucratic corruption has been regarded as a particularly viral form of bureau pathology. Once it enters the bureaucratic system of a public organization, it spreads quickly to all parts. If it is not diagnosed and treated it will eventually destroy public credibility and organizational effectiveness. Kempe argues that bureaucratic corruption in the Third World takes place in transactions between private individuals or firms and public officials. This results to misuse of public funds and the failure of public trust. Such corruption seriously undermines the effectiveness of government operations in its mandate of service delivery to the citizens.

According to Tøndel & Søreide (2008) a bureaucratic hierarchy, established to facilitate the functions of the state by delegating responsibilities, may contain structures that encourage principal-agent problems, instead of preventing collusion between agents and firms. This is an indication that bureaucratic corruption can be done through collusion from within or without the firm by the bureaucrats. Bureaucratic hierarchy acts as catalyst to enhance such form of corruption (Acemoglu & Verdier, 2000).

Muhammad, Mohammed & Kirfi (2013) rightly points out that bureaucratic corruption manifests itself in various forms. Such forms include: Bribery (the promise, offering or giving of a benefit that improperly affects the actions or decisions of a public servant)/ State Capture, Embezzlement (theft of resources by those entrusted with the authority and control), Fraud (actions or behaviors that fool others into providing a benefit that would not normally accrue), Extortion (coercing a person or entity to provide a benefit), Abuse of Power (using vested authority to improperly benefit), Conflict of Interest (acting or failing to act on a matter where one has interest), insider trading (abuse of privileged information), Favoritism (provision of services or resources according to personal affiliations), and Nepotism (ensuring family members benefit from State resources).

Further, bureaucratic corruption exists in various shades based on the nature of the project. Stansbury (2005) points out that bureaucratic corruption manifests itself in different forms in hard-core infrastructural projects depending on the following factors: Size of infrastructure projects-It is easier to hide large bribes and inflated claims in large projects than it is in small projects. Uniqueness of projects- Many major construction projects are one-off making costs difficult to compare, which in turn makes it easier to inflate costs or hide bribes. Government involvement -Insufficient controls on how government officials behave, combined with the complexity of projects, makes it relatively easy for officials to extract bribes. The number of contractual links provides an opportunity for someone to pay a bribe in exchange for the award of a contract. The number of phases each involving different management teams and requiring handovers of the completed phase to the contractors undertaking the next phase makes project oversight difficult. The complexity of projects-bribes and inflated claims can easily be hidden or blamed on other factors, for example, poor design or mismanagement. Lack of frequency of projects- major projects come at irregular intervals. Winning these projects may be critical to the survival or profitability of contractors, which provides an incentive to contractors to bribe. No single organization governs the industry- each profession or trade may have a different professional association, with different codes of conduct and levels of enforcement of these codes.

According to Calvill & Sohail (2007) bureaucratic corruption exists or take place in the different stages of infrastructural service delivery .The first stage is planning stages. Identification of projects not done with a cost-benefit analysis, projects used as vote winners/opportunities for personal gain, not as basis of national or regional priority and availability of financial resources, leading to projects that are unnecessary, planning in favor of high value infrastructure and against the interest of the poor, over-investment in capital goods (white elephant projects) at the expense of GDP growth. The second stage is inspection stages. Insufficient prior inspections, bribing inspectors .The third stage is design stage plus many more stages involved.

Izueke (2010) observes that collusion is also a powerful tool or form of corruption. He identified the following forms of collusion that are common to the local government system: a. collusion between supervisory ministries and local government chairmen; b. Collusion with citizen who benefit from the thieving public officers; c. Collusion with contractors to inflate contract prices or quotation. From the above enumerated forms of collusion one can infer that service delivery is a far cry from local government system.

Institutionalized corruption (bureaucratic corruption) incorporates characteristics of the tendering process that are in the hands of public officials who conduct the tender and suggests deliberate competition restriction (Fazekas, Tóth, & King, 2013). A simple way to fix tenders is to avoid the publication of the call for tenders in the official public procurement journal as this would make it harder for competitors to prepare a bid. This is only considered in non-open procedures as in open procedures publication is mandatory (Lengwiler &

Wolfstetter, 2006). While open competition is relatively hard to avoid in some tendering procedure types such as open procedures, others such as accelerated negotiated or negotiated without competition procedures are by default much less competitive; hence, using less open and transparent procedure types can indicate the deliberate limitation of competition that is corruption risks (Chong, Klien, & Saussier, 2015). Different types of evaluation criteria are prone to manipulation to different degrees, subjective, hard-to-quantify criteria often accompany rigged assessment procedures as it creates room for discretion and limits accountability mechanisms (OECD, 2007). If the time used for deciding on the submitted bids is excessively short or lengthened by legal challenge, it can also signal corruption risks. Snap decisions on large value tenders may reflect premeditated assessment, while legal challenge and the corresponding long decision period suggests outright violation of laws (Heggstad & Froystad, 2011).

Petty Corruption in infrastructure usually take place during the lateral stages of a project life cycle and may include the form of fees paid to secure services e.g. provision of electricity or access to clean water (Cavill & Sohail, 2007) and for a company, a small fee to get an invoice paid, to certify completion of the works or obtaining customs clearance for equipment and materials (Hawkins, 2013). This type of corruption involves small sums of money across a large number of individuals (Uslaner, 2009).

Grand Corruption usually take place during the early stages of the project life cycle, especially during the development of government policies (Butterworth and de la Harpe, 2009). High-level government officials – represented by legislators or elected public officials – may institute or manipulate policy in favour of particular interest groups (representing private sector interests and entities or individual units of public bureaucracy competing for higher budgets) in exchange for rents or side payments (Persson et al., 2010). Corruption during this stage may take place in the identification and selection of high value uneconomical projects, selecting project designs favoring particular firms and contracts being awarded to favored bidders, allowing extortion and political patronage (Hawkins, 2013). This form of corruption involves a relatively small number of individuals which acquire large sums of money and abuse their discretionary powers (Uslaner, 2009).

Unlike Aqsa (2014) who classifies corruption in two forms; Cytonn (2018) agrees with Asea (2018) who argues that bureaucratic corruption exists in three forms. Cytonn asserts that corruption can be classified as grand, petty and political, depending on the amount of money lost and the sector where it occurs. Grand corruption consists of acts committed at a high level of government that distort policies or the central functioning of the state, enabling leaders to benefit at the expense of the public good. Petty corruption refers to everyday abuse of entrusted power by low and mid-level public officials in their interactions with ordinary citizens, who often are trying to access basic goods or services in places like hospitals, schools, police departments, and other agencies. Political corruption is a manipulation of policies, institutions and rules of procedure in the allocation of resources and financing by political decision makers, who abuse their position to sustain their power, status and wealth.

In summing up, local government and indeed county governments are the public affair organ that is closer to the people as Odion et al (2009) puts it. Ezeani (2004), also view local government generally as veritable agent of development and grassroots participation in the democratic process. Unfortunately, corruption and indeed bureaucratic corruption has eaten into this realization in various forms. As aforementioned above, bureaucratic corruption exist in various forms. It can manifest itself in form of bribes, embezzlement, fraud and extortion, abuse of power, conflict of interest and abuse of privilege of information, favoritism and nepotism. Further as argued above, bureaucratic corruption can be manifest in misallocation of resources. Bureaucratic hierarchy may harbor bureaucratic corruption. It takes different shades depending on the nature of the project, that is, size of the project, uniqueness of project, government involvement, and complexity of projects and lack of frequency of projects. Bureaucratic corruption is also manifested or can take place at different levels of infrastructural project such as at planning stage, inspection stage, design stage construction stage,

implementation stage, service delivery stage, maintenance and management stage, billing system stage, disconnection stage and fault redress stage either as petty corruption, grand corruption or in political corruption.

The Effects of Bureaucratic Corruption on Hard- Core Infrastructural Service Delivery in Devolved Units

Groenendijk (2014) in analyzing the principal-agent theory, the model highlights the effects of corruption on the principal (P), agent (A) and the client (C). For instance C faces number of different problems; first of all he has to consider whether corruption in itself pays or not. The benefits of corruption for C consist of services rendered or the good provide by A, and /or not having to bear any deadweight costs. Groenendijk further says principal – agent theory points out that there are costs associated with corruption, such as the costs of finding the size of bribe, and the bribe itself. Also there are costs of keeping the transaction secret, the expected value of the penalty in case C gets caught, and moral costs. And in the event when C is caught and decision is made in favour of corruption; C becomes the principal to A. The greatest loser becomes P (citizens). For example ,considering corruption in a warding public-work contracts after C has won; passes the costs of corruption (notably the cost of the bribe) on to P either by simply increasing the price P has to pay ,or by doing substandard work.

Corruption has been the focus of an extensive literature (Graycar & Monaghan ,2015). Becker (1968) was among the first to emphasize the economic dimension of corruption, a calculative logic is at the roots of a corruptive behavior. He explained corruption in terms of a cost-benefit analysis in which a number of factors (the certainty of punishment, the benefits derivable etc.) combine to influence the decision to bribe. Along the same lines, other authors have recalled contractualism and agency theory by describing corruption as a deviation of the agent's behavior that favors his personal interest over the collective (Banfield, 1985). Among influences of corruption on economic dimensions is its effect on service delivery. Runaway corruption affects service delivery negatively and much more in public enterprises which are bureaucratic by nature.

Services are failing because they are falling short of their potential to improve outcomes. They are often inaccessible or prohibitively expensive. But even when accessible, they are often dysfunctional, extremely low in technical quality and unresponsive to the needs of diverse citizens. This state of affair is attributed to corruption (World Bank, 2004). Development depends largely on providing public goods such as infrastructure. Yet despite considerable investment, infrastructure services are widely perceived to be unsatisfactory. Internationally, it is recognized that corruption (including bribery, embezzlement, kickbacks and fraud) in construction projects undermines the sustainability of infrastructure services. Furthermore, corruption poses significant risks to construction and engineering companies themselves. More specifically, corruption constitutes an important constraint to the sustainability of public service provision. For example, corruption raises the cost and lowers the quality of infrastructure, resulting in sub-standard infrastructure and poor infrastructure management. These services are normally the responsibility of a local government, but may be provided by the private sector and non-governmental organizations (Calvill & Sohail, 2007)

Just like Calvill & Sohail, DFID (2002) recognizes that the lack of transparency in procurement systems and independent oversight of the process often facilitate corrupt practices. Stansbury (2005) argues that corruption in procurement generates immense opportunities for payoffs with comparatively low risk of detection and punishment. According to Pope (2000) opportunities for corruption in public sector procurement are created by complicated procedures and the large amounts of money involved create incentives for corrupt behavior. Tanzi and Davoodi (1998) argue that corruption in procurement seems to reduce the productivity of public investment, reduce the quality of existing infrastructure, and reduce the capital spending productivity and as a consequence lower the growth rate of the country. As argued above it is clear corruption and more so bureaucratic corruption undermines the roles of government and more so the delivery of infrastructural services.

In addition, public sector corruption manifested in bureaucracy leads to misallocation of resources and thereby triggering a drastic fall in both the quantity and quality of services provided. Therefore creates a loss of trust in the legitimacy of political system which seriously undermining its acceptance by the citizens. This obviously escalates the deficit trust between the government and its citizenry. As stated above, it is clear that any form of bureaucratic corruption undermines service delivery and creates principal (citizens) –government (agent) problems. And though they have not openly stated, it can be argued that for any of the above from of bureaucratic corruption to penetrate within the bureaucracy there must be network of bureaucrats with same self-interests (Calvill & Sohail, 2007).

Different people, organizations and scholar has pointed out the effects of corruption on service delivery especially in government. Asea (2018) points out that corruption is a global concern that has caused wide-reaching damages. Nilson (2009) in quoting a World Bank study conducted in 2002 stated that the world spends 1 trillion dollar per year on bribes. Consequently, the damage is acute for instance; firstly, corruption undermines democracy and good governance by subverting formal processes such as election and government policy (USAID, 1999). Secondly, it results in biased decision-making, as considerations of personal enrichment take precedence over the establishment of rights for all. Thirdly, corruption obstructs justice, as it becomes biased and unfair. In a system of corruption, judgments are not equal for equal cases; they are mostly false and not impartial (Grisman, 2009). Fourthly, corruption creates inefficiencies in public expenditure by diverting resources and policy decisions to easily corruptible sectors. Fifthly, corruption slows economic development and reduces the quality of government services by creating sizeable distortions (World Bank, 2013). Sixthly, corruption causes loss of government revenue as businesses go underground, and it also increases the tax burden. Seventhly, it infringes on fundamental human rights to fair treatment. All persons are entitled to be treated equally, and when one person bribes a public official, he acquires a privileged status in relation to others. Hence, the latter will be hurt (World Bank, 2013). In addition, corruption results in the loss of legitimacy and respect for the socio-legally constituted authority and maintenance of a just social order.

According to MacDonald & Majeed (2011) although corruption, that is, misuse of public power for private gain, is disliked in its essence because of its detrimental effects on the development of a country, it is pervasive and exists with varying degrees, in every country in the world. They assert that in recent years, international organizations such as the United Nations and the World Bank have made corruption a significant focus of their agenda and have made significant attempts to curb corruption in the world. According to Transparency International (2018), the corruption perception index (CIP) 2018 reveals that the continued failure of most countries to significantly control corruption is contributing to a crisis of democracy and service delivery around the world. Corruption has increased over recent years. MacDonald & Majeed (2011) states that it is widely accepted by economists, development practitioners and policy makers that corruption is a problem of developing countries. However, recently a number of scandals over corruption have shown that rich nations, supposedly free from corruption are also suffering from its effects.

According to the Slovakia Corruption Report (2018) bureaucratic corruption is a major issue in Slovakia. Political corruption is widespread, contracts are awarded to party supporters, and tenders are overpriced and questionably managed. Consequently, the country loses a lot of money. In turn it becomes the burden to the citizens, who end up getting poor service delivery especially in the hardcore such as building and roads.

Though Netherlands is regarded as corruption free country, according to a report of the Centre for the Study of Democracy, corruption in the Netherlands is more prevalent in the public sector than in the political sphere (De Graaf et al., 2008). This is as a result of burdensome government bureaucracy. In the public sector corruption is more common at local levels than in central administrative bodies. These are the construction companies that pay bribes to local officials in relation to access to public contracts and making the contracts profitable. Corrupt officials embezzle funds and also ask for kickbacks. And in regaining and maximizing profits contracted companies provide sub-standard services (Transparency International, 2015).

Norway is looked at as one of the cleanest economies in the globe, although in recent years, according to MacDonald & Muhammad (2011) in quoting the Global Integrity Report (2009), corruption is increasing in this country as well. They allude to four different cases; the rehabilitation of public buildings has been exposed to corruption as civil servants responsible for the rehabilitation received bribes. The CEO of two public companies in Norway misused his position for private gain and the officer is said to have transferred more than 100 million Norwegian kroners (US\$ 17.7 million) from the two public companies into his private accounts. As a result it is clear that poor quality of service and unnecessary high cost of service was realized out of this bureaucratic corruption.

One of the critical policy issues in African management today is bureaucratic corruption. This problem has in some countries reached such proportions as to frustrate good policy intentions and to paralyze management operations (David & Tshiabukole, 2007).

The case is not much different in South Africa; the local government is constitutionally assigned a broad range of functions that entail responsibility for infrastructure services. Corruption has however eaten into the infrastructural sector where for instance one of most prevalent form of corruption is abuse of the tendering and procurement procedures for private gain. Local government is considered to be particularly vulnerable to corruption given both the size of its operations, the size of its budget allocation and the role of that councils play in the tendering process. Consequently, provision of infrastructural service fails to meet the required standards and the provision of infrastructure suffers (Hollands, 2007). Further, Gossel (2017) terms this type of corruption as bureaucratic corruption. Gossel in his part alludes that bureaucratic corruption has led to the patronage and state of capture machinery. The capital allocated for service delivery is wasted, the private sector is crowded out, and the monopolizing positions of dysfunctional state owned enterprises distort the economy. At the local level ,he argues that unqualified party loyalists-or close associates-are assigned jobs to disseminate services inefficiently from shrinking pool of capital while further extracting rents through a sub-layer of corruption(bureaucratic corruption).Consequently, the citizens pay bribes for mispriced and inefficient state services. In turn, as the looting via state capture and municipal corruption intensifies, services provision and delivery declines.

In Nigeria, the effect of corruption is rife as Egberi & Madubueze (2014) put it. In their study, they found out that due to the privileged position of the Public Servants (Agents) to public resources and information, they tend to abuse these privileges to the detriments of the 'Principals' (Nigerian citizens) hence poor service delivery especially in the infrastructure sector. This act contradicts the essence of government existence more so local government. Further, Egberi & Madubueze asserts that the existence of government is to deliver social services that will make life meaningful and worth living. Local governments as a tier of government were created to bring government closer to the people at the rural communities and for transformation of lives at that level. One of the ways of bringing government closer to the people at the grassroots is through the delivery of social services in a satisfactory, timely, effective and adequate manner. Regrettably, the authors assert that the realization of this objective has been constrained by extreme corruption in Local Government. Corruption remains a major problem which has constrained local government from contributing meaningfully to the uplifting of the standard of living of the local people. This problem is manifest in almost every local government area in Nigeria. It is rife in the area of revenue declaration by collectors, to award of contracts, and embezzlement of local government funds by Chairmen, Councilors and other officials of local governments. This bureaucratic corruption therefore directly affects the social and economic pillars such as infrastructure of the country and indeed the local governments.

Generally, transport infrastructure and indeed hard-core infrastructure provision from roads and to buildings waterways involves large amounts of public funds in very complex projects. It is hardly a surprise that all across Europe, but especially in high corruption risk countries, it is a primary target of corrupt elites. Improving the coverage and quality of transport infrastructure is key for economic development as it is a core public good

supporting economic transactions, hence growth in general. Corruption in transport infrastructure provision can compromise public goals (Fazekas & Tóth, 2018).

According to Fazekas & Tóth again, these public goals can be compromised in various ways: firstly, corruption in transport infrastructure provision is likely to distort spending structure, in particular to bias public investment towards high value, high complexity investments into new infrastructure as opposed to spending on maintenance and operations. Voters may force governments to commit to inefficiently high value projects (that is, new transport infrastructure instead of maintenance) so that the choice of future governments is restricted, even though it would not have been preferred *ex post* (Glazer, 1989). Interestingly, such long-term commitment devices may also serve clientelism in as much as large projects cement long term rents enjoyed by a favored community and bureaucrats even if political leadership changes. This expected distortion is demonstrated by Fazekas and Tóth while quoting Tanzi & Davoodi (1997) who show that higher level of corruption in a country (measured by perception indices) is associated with increased public investment, but with lower expenditures on operations and maintenance. Given this point of view, it has to be investigated to what degree bureaucratic corruption enhances biases transport infrastructure, and indeed hard-core infrastructure in general, spending towards high value projects in local governments.

Price inflation can manifest itself in for example wages or material costs in the awarded contract or only later during contract implementation (European Court of Auditors, 2013). Although without connecting it to corruption risks *per se*, Flyvbjerg, Holm, & Buhl (2003) shows that price escalation (that is, cost overrun) is indeed a common phenomenon in case of transport infrastructure projects both for road, rail and fixed links (bridges and tunnels), and although in a varying magnitude it is evidenced in developed and developing countries as well. Furthermore, Flyvbjerg, Holm, & Buhl (2004) also show that price escalation is strongly affected by the length of the implementation phase, hence underlying the connection between costs and implementation period. Based on this literature, the effect of corruption risk on infrastructure prices in terms of % increase or total cash increase should be explored empirically at the local levels of governments to determine further implications of price inflation on hard-core infrastructure service delivery. Fazekas & Tóth argues that corruption in transport infrastructure provision is likely to increase prices even when taking project specifications are given. In addition to this, corruption in transport infrastructure can contribute to delayed and low quality provision, in extreme cases failed completion altogether (Lewis-Faupel, Neggers, Olken, & Pande, 2014).

In EU funded road projects in 2000-2013, the average delay was 41% or 9 months of the initial estimate (European Court of Auditors, 2013). Significant time overruns (6 to 12 months) were also apparent in a range of Eastern European and Central Asian countries' road projects financed by the World Bank (Alexeeva, Queiroz, & Ishihara 2011). Similarly, in a wide set of African developing countries also experienced more than a year delay in contract implementation in their World Bank funded road projects (Alexeeva et al., 2008). Delayed provision and long implementation is also fertile ground for inflating costs as it is pointed out in Flyvbjerg et al. (2004). Although, time overruns are not straightforward indications of corruption (complex projects can have unforeseen complications), weak supervision and enforcement of the initial contracts give rise to corruption risks especially within the bureaucracy. While construction delays are easy to detect, assessing implementation quality is less straightforward (for example, the effects are only visible after years). Gillanders (2013) – quoting World Bank survey data – shows that perceived corruption is significantly and positively related to the percentage of firms identifying transportation (that is, its quality) as a major constraint both at the country and regional level. By extension While there is probably the scantest thorough research on project non-completions, they are likely to represent the most severe corruption harm and can become systemic at certain places. The tragedy of unfinished infrastructure projects is that without full completion, most projects cannot be used at all. Despite the clearly relevant corruption risks at the implementation stage, due to the lack of adequate data and the complexity of the quality-corruption relationship, the connection between corruption risks and delayed or

low quality provision at local level governments, this study needs to test this determine parameters involved and empirical evidence on the same.

According to Fazekas & Tóth (2018) while these different forms of direct corruption costs in transport infrastructure provision may occur jointly or substitute for each other, they are likely to carry different total social costs. If corruption only increases the price of infrastructure without impacting on project design, infrastructure quality, delivery time, or overall completion, total social cost is close to the direct cost. However, if corruption's direct impact goes beyond prices, additional indirect costs are likely inflicted on the society such as non-available infrastructure or unreliable provision. In order to affirm this, this study aims to unearth these issues to determine the effect of bureaucratic corruption which occur in the fore mentioned forms on delivery of infrastructure services and more so hard-core infrastructural services.

In Uganda, according to the African Peer Review Mechanism, all the informants in Uganda, including political leaders and appointed officials, agreed that corruption is now institutionalized (Asea,2018). This standpoint is also backed by public opinion, which consistently perceives high levels of corruption in political and public service institutions both at the national and local government levels (Mwenda & Tangri, 2005).Bureaucratic corruption takes place in service delivery and rule enforcement. It has two sides: demand-induced and supply-induced. The Ugandan political machinery and bureaucrats (agents) have ensured that the practice of corruption thrives to benefit their interests at the expense of the poor majority (principals) (Badru, 2013).Consequently, corruption has caused wide-reaching damages: firstly, corruption undermines democracy and good governance by subverting formal processes such as election and government policy (USAID, 1999). Secondly, it results in biased decision-making, as considerations of personal enrichment take precedence over the establishment of rights for all. Thirdly, corruption obstructs justice, as it becomes biased and unfair. In a system of corruption, judgments are not equal for equal cases; they are mostly false and not impartial (Grisman, 2009). Fourthly, corruption creates inefficiencies in public expenditure by diverting resources and policy decisions to easily corruptible sectors. Fifthly, it slows economic development and reduces the quality of government services by creating sizeable distortions (World Bank, 2013). Sixthly, corruption causes loss of government revenue as businesses go underground, and it also increases the tax burden. Seventhly, it infringes on fundamental human rights to fair treatment. All persons are entitled to be treated equally, and when one person bribes a public official he acquires a privileged status in relation to others. Hence, the latter will be hurt (World Bank, 2013). Conclusively, corruption results in the loss of legitimacy and respect for the socio-legally constituted authority and maintenance of a just social order. As much as this literature indeed extensively highlights bureaucratic corruption and its effect in Uganda in general, it fails to specifically address the effect bureaucratic corruption in provision of hard-core infrastructural services at the local government which is the yeast of this study. However, as it is argued above public services in any government includes infrastructural services, which is one of the roles of government. This implies that if bureaucratic corruption eats into other government sectors, infrastructural sector is not exceptional. And the effects this practice thereon are evident as illustrated above.

According to Tanzi & Davoodi (1997) corruption has adverse effects on investment and economic growth. A payment of a briber to get an investment license, for example, clearly reduces incentive to invest. Corruption particularly bureaucratic or political distorts the decision making process connected with public investment projects (Grisman, 2009). Corruption is likely to increase the number of projects undertaken in a country, and to change the design of these projects by enlarging size and complexity. For instance corruption reduces expenditure on other sectors that are perceived to have lower bribe returns but increase expenditure on public sectors such as infrastructure which has high opportunities to extract high rents from public expenditure (Mauro, 1998).

Shrabani (2009) opines that corruption affects efficiency in service delivery. The effect of corruption on efficiency is based two opposing strands (Rose-Ackerman, 1978).The efficiency-enhancing stand view corruption as increasing efficiency because corruption 'greases the wheels'. The opposing strand ,labeled as

efficiency-reducing, views corruption as having a damaging impact on efficiency; those 'rusty wheels' are put there in the first place to attract bribes. The efficiency-enhancing school of thought suggests that in developing countries, corruption may actually improve efficiency and help growth (Huntington, 1968). According to Shrabani (2009) in a system where goods and services are allocated by queue, politics, and random selection, or merit, corruption may instead allocate goods and services according to willingness and ability to pay. Myrdal (1968) however asserts that corrupt officials may instead of spending up the process cause administrative delays in order to attract more bribes hence creating a vicious cycle that delays services to the citizens .

Provision of hard –core infrastructural services, in many jurisdiction, requires one to attain licenses and permits from relevant authority (Kluwer,2018).Therefore, as Tanzi and Davoodi (1997) stated above bribes increases the cost of attaining such legal requirements hence making it expensive to provide infrastructural services. However, from the above arguments on efficiency-enhancing stand; Huntington (1968) fails to empirically support his assertion .He fails to unearth how the vicious cycle syndrome of bribery could be addressed. For instance In an event where the briber gets a tender for instance to construct a road, what guarantee is there to prove that the contractor could provide the services because the bribery trend might continue to cover up the implementation stage of the project hence ghost project.

In Kenya, according to Kempe (2014) corruption is systemic and goes beyond individuals to the structural and institutional levels .He furthers asserts that the culture of corruption has grown roots in Kenyan society at large and become endemic. Institutions, which were designed for the regulation of the relationships between citizens and the State, are being used instead for the personal enrichment of public officials (politicians and bureaucrats) and other corrupt private agents (individuals, groups, and businesses). Corruption persists in Kenya primarily because there are people in power who benefit from it and the existing governance institutions lack both the will and capacity to stop them from doing so.

Maina (2013) quotes a survey carried out by EACC (2010) in the health sector in the country which found out that corruption has adverse consequences in the health sector. Among the findings; corruption was found to drain resources (finances, medical and non – medical supplies) leaving other functions (operations and Maintenance) underfunded hence, impacting negatively on the quality of services delivered. Further unofficial charges increases the cost of accessing health care services leading to marginalization of the poor in the society. Corruption was also found to accelerate the problem of counterfeit drugs in the market. The effect is not different in other sectors such as infrastructure. Corruption and indeed bureaucratic corruption is contagious in nature; it is transmitted from one sector to another (Attila, 2008).

According to Sieber (2012) the construction sector is prone to corruption. Survey evidence of local and international firms at the country level suggests that construction is an industry particularly prone to corruption-both related to government contracting and to circumvent regulation. Construction firms have significantly large bribe budget and they bribe more often (Kenny,2007)The lack of transparency in contracting process for large scale infrastructure projects can have devastating consequences for economic and social development (Transparency International, 2011). Collier & Hoeffler (2005) qualified the impact of corruption in infrastructure and concluded that corruption delays and reduces expenditure on infrastructure investment. Also corruption reduces the growth generated by given expenditure on infrastructure investment and above all corruption reduces the quality of infrastructure services and limits access especially for the poor.

Fonshell (2018) argues that the bottom line is corruption can be seen in every facet of daily life in Kenya, from citizens' interactions with police officers to the choices made by government officials. It is estimated that corruption accounts for 8% of the nation's Gross Domestic Product and the 2012 Kenyan treasury estimates showed that 20-30 percent of the budget was lost each year due to dishonest acts such as fraudulent procurement (Harrington et. al., 2013).This indicates that corruption can seriously limit the development of national economies and undermine good governance. It erodes stability and trust, and it damages the ethos of

democratic governance. Its effects can seriously limit the development of national economies and undermine good governance. Corruption erodes stability and trust, and it damages the ethos of democratic governance (Fonshell, 2018). This literature has not directly shown effects of corruption on infrastructure but it is important to note that infrastructural development is a pillar to the stability of country's economy.

In support of this point of view Murage (2011) asserts that senior public officials in other branches in government have also voiced their worry about the impact of corruption in Kenya. For instance, the then Deputy Speaker of Parliament, during a speech at the opening ceremony of a Parliamentary pre-budget workshop in March 2011, expressed concern over rampant graft in government. Murage further reports that then Deputy Speaker said that the bulk of the revenue collected by the Kenyan government gets lost through corruption and that is why many government-funded projects have stalled. He went on to say that a paltry 30 per cent of public cash is spent on projects while the other 70 per cent is stolen by bureaucrats, politicians, and contractors and, as a result, Kenya loses billions to corruption. This concern by that then Deputy Speaker also demonstrates how persistent and entrenched corruption is in Kenya. The Deputy Speaker notes that each year the National Taxpayers Association (NTA) conducts audits which continue to show an increase in the proportion of public funds for local development projects that has been allocated to ghost projects, embezzled, or outright stolen (NTA, 2011).

Kenya has moved from a passive to an active phase where public servants, in particular, do not wait to be approached and bribed, for example, but actively and boldly solicit individuals to offer bribes or other favour in return for the provision of public services (Hope, 2012). The ultimate consequence of this is that the integrity, credibility, and professionalism of the public service have been compromised, and governance indicators such as government effectiveness (including the quality of public service delivery, the quality of the public service and the degree of its independence from political pressures, the quality of policy formulation and implementation, and the credibility of the government's commitment to such policies) and control of corruption (Kempe, 2014).

In addition, corruption diminishes government services. People don't get the benefit of their taxes because the money has disappeared into someone's pocket. Money spent to deliver public goods such as safe roads and health care services doesn't go as far (Chiefs of Mission in Kenya, 2014). Similarly, theft, embezzlement, and fraud by public officials reduce the availability of funds for development-related activities. For instance, in December 2010, the then Permanent Secretary of the Ministry of Finance, in testimony before a parliamentary committee, said that each year corruption and mismanagement of public funds rob Kenya of Ksh 270 billion (Ochami & Njiraini, 2010).

Conclusively, Kempe (2014) opines that corruption and bad governance in Kenya not only distort the availability of funds for development activities but also directly affect development assistance partnerships. The USA and the UK are Kenya's two biggest bilateral donors and they seem to be constantly scolding the Kenyan government and/or withholding or suspending development assistance from it due to persistent corruption.

As much as Kempe, 2014, Hope, 2012 and Murage, 2011 categorically affirms that bureaucratic corruption is rife in Kenya in various forms, and their effect on governance, they have not explicitly pointed out the effects of bureaucratic corruption on devolved units especially on the devolved functions such as provision of infrastructural services such as county roads. However, it is important to note that the effects of bureaucratic corruption on government services as Kempe states, though he has not mentioned directly, encompasses provision of infrastructural services to the citizens (principals) by government through the bureaucrats (agents).

One of the critical policy issues in African management today is bureaucratic corruption. This problem has in some countries reached such proportions as to frustrate good policy intentions and to paralyze management operations (David & Tshiabukole, 2007). Formation of county government in Kenya in itself is a policy that is meant to ease the burden of service delivery but has always been dogged by corruption. According to (

Odhiambo,2019) He reports that senators and anti-corruption agency at a Fourth Annual Legislative Summit in Kisumu asserted that governors compromise MCAs by awarding them tenders, which make it difficult for them to do oversight role. Contracts are given to ward reps at the expense of qualified and deserving Kenyans. Consequently, poor quality service is realized at counties. Even though, however, bureaucratic corruption is not directly alluded to, it is evidently clear that county bureaucrats are involved in the concern departments are involved to set the records 'straight' hence bureaucratic corruption.

According to Omondi (2014) almost every county government has flouted tendering rules and violated staffing guidelines by rewarding cronies and relatives. Several counties in western Kenya (Mbula, 2019) misappropriated billions of shillings set aside for development projects, a good number of projects remain incomplete years after the expiry of the time set for construction. Migori, Busia, Homa Bay, Kisumu, Kisii, Siaya and Vihiga are among the counties which their projects have been questioned.

As seen above most literature looks at effect of corruption on governance, development, and economy of a country but there is insufficient literature on the effect of bureaucratic corruption on infrastructure and indeed hard-core infrastructure in devolved units in Kenya hence a gap this study seeks to fill. Nevertheless, few literatures have been recorded on corruption and infrastructure in other regions such as West Africa countries such as Nigeria and Ghana; however little or none has been written on effect bureaucratic corruption and hard – core infrastructural service delivery.

The Correlation between Bureaucratic Corruption and Infrastructural Service Delivery in devolved units

Bureaucratic Corruption has some link to infrastructural service delivery in general since corruption itself affects service delivery in public and private sectors. Corruption is a global phenomenon (Kanu and Osinbajo, 1990); the issue of private and public bureaucratic corruption has become part and parcel of the large socio-economic and political misnomer that has inundated the Nigerian state and society. Corruption undermines not only the public support for government, but also the good governance, administrative capacity, and reliability of the Nigerian government. Important development have conspired to force a revolutionary reassessment to the fact that only a few now doubt that corruption exerts a heavy cost upon social, economic, political, service delivery and structural development of Nigeria. Corruption is (Anifowose, 2002) a pervasive phenomenon whose practices have become synonymous with governance, and consequently, has become the bane of the Nigerian society. Corruption is a general malaise pervading both the public and private sector organizations in Nigeria.

Rasul and Rogger (2013) opine that establishing a causal relation between management practices for bureaucrats and public sector projects delivered is not straight forward given that exogenous or experimental variation in such equilibrium practices is unlikely to be observed. We present six core findings linking civil service management practices and public service de-livery in Nigeria. First, the management practices bureaucrats operate under matter: both dimensions of practice have robust and significant correlations with project completion rates. The autonomy for bureaucrats corresponds to a significantly higher project completion rate. Some research find management practices correlate to project quality in similar ways as documented for project completion rates: higher levels of autonomy for bureaucrats are associated with projects being of significantly higher quality; higher levels of performance-based incentives are associated with projects being of significantly lower quality, all else equal

On autonomy, viewed through the lens of models of authority in organizations (Baker et al.1999], a principal is more likely to grant autonomy to an agent in the following scenarios: (i) tasks that are considered less important; (ii) tasks that require more technical competency; (iii) when the principal has a greater span of control; (iv) when agents have expertise. It is in these circumstances that we expect the provision of autonomy to have especially positive impacts on the organization's effectiveness as measured by project completion rates.

Of importance in examining the link between bureaucratic corruption and service delivery in devolved units would be the parameters to use. In this connection as Rasul and Rogger assert (in 2013 above), this is much defined by projects undertaken by bureaucratic organs to their completion rate on one hand and projects in relation to service delivery quality on the other hand. From a broader view, these become visible in bureaucratic structures in what is described by Anifowose (2002) as another situation favourable to corruption is when bribes serve as incentive payments for bureaucrats to do their jobs well because of low pay and inadequate monitoring. Queue managers/administrators and documentation officers for instance could accept pay-offs to work quickly and to favour those who value their time highly. The situation could arise when private individuals and firms seek to lower costs of taxes, duties and regulations imposed on them by government, especially where such payments are considered high. Individuals and firms may pay for relief from these costs for example, by colluding with tax collectors and customs officials to lower the sums collected. Contract awards and concessions are further incentives to corrupt practices.

Despite the link in project completion and service delivery quality, others observe the nature of bureaucratic corruption as exacerbating service delivery, where infrastructures are part and parcel. Agboola (2009) opines that the causes of corruption in Nigeria are multifaceted and diverse, these includes, low salary of public officials, job insecurity, problem of extended family, lack of transparency and accountable political process, lack of effective incentive mechanism for public officials, lack of effective reporting system cultural aspects and lack of independent and effective media. This to him has relations to do with infrastructure service delivery, though he fails to elaborate how each cause relates to SD. Further to this, he uses a structural analysis to explain the link thus another situation favourable to corruption is leadership by bad examples, when the head is sick then the functioning of the rest of the body is adversely affected, so goes on adage.

In a study (Damoah et'al, 2018) conducted to explore how corruption impacts the failure of government projects in developing countries with evidence from the Ghanaian context using the perceptions of project management practitioners, contractors, government officials, and the general public on the subject. The findings indicated that corruption influences government project failure on all failure criteria used for evaluation. However, strongly, corruption influences failure at two levels: project management and product phase. At project management level, corruption has direct influence, while at the product phase level, the influence is indirect.

Relationships can be concluded on a number of facets; existence, non-existence, or tending toward. Predisposition of factors likely to cause a linkage similarly indicates presence of relationship. In this study, most failure of government projects in developing countries are affected by corruption. At governmental level using the nature and existential capacity of governments are bureaucratic systems hence corruption here is bureaucratic. As affirmed by the study of Damoah et'al, an influence at project management and product phase can be construed sufficiently as impediments to infrastructural service delivery.

In this regard, definitively, service delivery is a component of business that defines the interaction between providers and clients where the provider offers a service, whether that to be information or a task, and the client either finds value or loses value as a result. Good service delivery provides clients with an increase in value. Service delivery framework is a set of principles, standards, policies and constraints to be used to guide the designs, development, deployment, operation and retirement of services delivered by a service provider with a view to offering a consistent service experience to a specific user community in a specific business context (Kim; 2013). The experience of value increase following set procedures portrays acceptable outcome on service delivery which would expected in running projects within bureaucracies and other organizations.

Defining government undertakings as bureaucratic activities, government projects play an important role in national development (Alic, 2008) and her policies often translate into programs and projects (Bitler & Karoly, 2015). Growth witnessed in the past two to three decades in emerging economies indicates that government

projects are inevitable in national development (Gichoya, 2005). The success of these projects is central to government performance (Alzahrani & Emsley, 2013). Nevertheless, many of these projects face several setbacks, such as total abandonment (Kumar & Best, 2006), cost deviation (Aziz, 2013), schedule deviation (Fallahnejad, 2013), scope deviation (Liu, Chen, Chenm, & Sheu, 2011), and stakeholder dissatisfaction (Ahonen & Savolainen, 2010).

In reference to factors that link bureaucratic corruption to infrastructural service delivery elsewhere and Kenya, it is imperative first and foremost to point that in government structure where there is national and county or rather different levels exist, there is certainty that the decentralized units form the bedrock of political parties that form and run the bureaucratic structures. This means many factors are at play in matters service delivery that emanates from governing elite that trickles down to the devolved units.

The corrupt practices in the country may be influenced by other factors as well. First, the cultural orientation of the country may be reflected in the implementation of government projects. Hofstede's (1983) six cultural dimensions may explain why corruption exists in government projects. These dimensions include power distance, individualism, masculinity, uncertainty avoidance, long-term orientation, and indulgence. He explains Ghanaian society is hierarchical in nature, practicing a master-servant relationship, where the rich and those in authority are revered (The Hofstede Centre, 2016). The scenario here is what makes bureaucracy what it is. This gives leeway for government project leaders to use power to divert project resources for personal use.

The political culture on the other hand may influence corruption to cause government project failure. Ghana practices multiparty democracy, and this has led to partisan politics (Asunka, 2016). This may influence corrupt practices, as empirical studies in politics show that electoral controls over politicians tend to suffer when voters are strongly attached to a political party (Kayser & Wlezien, 2011). There is a positive relationship between partisan politics and the accountability of political leaders (Besley, 2007).

In agreement with prior studies and political agency models, Asunka (2016) found that Ghanaians fail to hold their political leaders accountable in districts where there is a strong attachment to political parties and vice versa. Third, the management and administration practices within the public sector of the country may also influence corrupt practices that may influence government project failure. There is a high level of bureaucratic and institutional bottlenecks within the public administration system (Amoako & Lyon, 2014).

Saha and Gounder (2013) further found that corruption has a significant social effect. Paunov (2016) identified corruption as a factor that impedes innovation. Athanasouli and Goujard (2015) also found that corruption impacts firm management quality. In an assessment of the relationship between corruption and GDP, Pellegrini and Gerlagh (2004) found a positive relationship. Some studies have been devoted to the relationship between corruption and project performance. For instance, Sonuga, Aliboh, and Oloke (2002) identified corruption as one of the factors that lead to project failure in Nigeria. In a comparative analysis of drivers and barriers to the adoption of relational contract practices in construction projects using Sydney and Beijing as examples, Ling, Ong, Ke, Wang, and Zou (2014).

According to Damoah et al (2018), the respondents in a study revealed that in some cases, corrupt practices may result in the total abandonment of government projects and suggested that this could be traced to politics. The contractors and project management practitioners perceived that in some cases, project abandonment occurs because of government appointed project leaders' demands for bribes from contractors. If the contractors refuse, the project leaders would do anything possible to make the projects fail. The analysis of data showed that some Ghanaian government project deliverables often do not meet requirements as a result of corruption. Shoddy work is produced in some circumstances, especially in projects that are directly awarded by Ghanaian government officials. Thus, the quantity and quality of the deliverables are sometimes compromised because of corruption. This was attributed to the lack of supervision by government consultants and regulatory bodies such as quality control officers; hence, contractors end up using the wrong products when carrying out projects.

Corruption undermines the development of poor countries as it impacts the economy directly by reducing economic investments, hindering competition, distorting markets and increasing income inequalities (Chetwynd, Frances & Spector. 2003). It also erodes the institutional capacity of governments to deliver quality public service and diverts public investment away from major public needs into capital projects. To the country's development, it destroys the government's desire of raising the sustainable level of living of the poor people and hinders the provision of the opportunities to develop their fullest potential (Staudt, 1991).

The patterns of corruption (Madinda, 2014) vary from society to society and overtime. Its conceptualization has attracted many perceptions and approaches. This leads to the difficulties on how the term can be comprehensively defined. Khan as cited by Lawal, (2007) defines corruption as an act which deviates from the formal rules of conduct governing the actions of someone in a position of public authority because of private motive such as wealth, power or status. The term was derived from the Latin word "Corruptus" which means "to break". It symbolizes a breakdown of ethical and moral values of systems and institutions of governance, societal traditions and personal behaviors (ADB, 2003).

This affects the lives of people and their development in many ways e.g. most of governments divert their budgets from social valuable goods like education and health and tends to increase public spending on capital intensive investments that's resulted into more opportunities for kickbacks such as defense contracts and undermines public service delivery (World Bank, 2001). As Todaro (1977) related development with economic growth, corruption therefore has direct consequences on both economic and governance (political) perspectives.

In examining the relationship between development and corruption, Lawal (2007) argued that corruption is a real enemy to economic development because it gives the particular country poor image and uncertainty in interpersonal and business relationship. Corruption affects foreign and domestic investment as it reduces incentives to both foreign and domestic investors as part of revenues goes to individuals instead of being added to the government revenue (Chetwynd et al, 2003). The development is also threatened by poor collection of taxes and now companies operate under informal procedures because of corruption; the effect comes when taxes are reduced in exchange for payoffs of tax officers.

Madinda (2014) puts forward that corruption weakens political institutions and mass participation in good governance which in turn destroys the economic development. There is a very close relationship between development, social capital and trust. As corruption rises, it tends to damage the public trusts in government institution. The trust again is very important aspect in strengthening social capital and the social capital helps people to regain trust and be willing to invest in productive activities to boost up development. So if people distrust their government and the social capital is destroyed then the investment in productive activities will be ruined, because in order for people to invest there must be a trust (Chetwynd, et al, 2003).

Tanzi and Davoodi (1998) are among the firsts to investigate the link between corruption and poor quality of the scope delivered. Gillanders (2014) shows that regions with higher corruption than the national average tend to have worse infrastructure than others. (Van de Graaf and Sovacool, 2014) demonstrate that corruption can be a source of project failure, especially in highly corrupt countries. (Ma and Xu, 2009) identify two major acts of corruption:

- i. To obtain unlawful the qualifications during bidders and/or tender;
- ii. To raise prices or reduce the quality of engineering standards during construction.

Corruption affects projects and megaprojects performance leading to the delivery of works with limited social

benefit, poor economic returns and over-cost and building poor quality infrastructure in the wrong place. Corruption affects the quality of the project starting from the project preparation and it continues during its implementation with major acts of corruption (Wells, 2014).

Locateli et'al (2016), records a summary of how corruption negatively affects project performance as below:

- i. It delays delivery times and increases infrastructure costs.
- ii. It reduces the potential economy of infrastructure because sub-optimal projects are implemented.
- iii. It reduces efficiency, favouring construction firms with corrupt connections rather than the most efficient ones.
- iv. It reduces the quality of infrastructure services.
- v. It increases the operating cost of providing a given level of infrastructure services. It limits access, especially for the poor, because of the higher price of service associated with higher costs in construction, operation and maintenance.
- vi. It favours the creation of monopolies and market concentrations.

Corruption is one of the key issues for public policies. It is one of the major impediments to the development of emerging countries and to further improve the quality of life in developed countries (Loosemore and Lim, 2015). Tabish and Jha (2012) show a positive correlation between “corruption free indicators” and professional standard, transparency, fairness of punishment, procedural compliance and contractual compliance. Several factors can undermine the performance of projects, such as complexity or “technological sublime”, weakness in organizational design and capabilities, optimism bias, strategic misinterpretation or even certain project characteristics, etc. (Garemo et al., 2015).

Corruption may have paradoxical effects. For example, one study on Morocco found that corruption in land reform was functional for the survival of the regime and dysfunctional for the economy (Johnston, 1986). But over time, the onus of scholarship has shifted decisively away from arguments in the 1950-60s about the utility of corruption (Huntington, 1968) to mounting evidence in the 1980-90s of the costs of corruption (Susan, 1978). Contributing factors included the spread of democratic regimes (in which the costs of corruption were quite significant) in Anderson (2003) as well as new tools to measure corruption and quantify some of its impact (World Bank, 2005).

Corruption slows economic growth primarily by reducing investment (Mauro, 1998) but also by reducing the quantity and effectiveness of international aid and the quality of infrastructure, and is associated with weak rule of law, insecure property rights and declining government effectiveness, which are also detrimental to investment and growth (Kaufmann, 2004). The political consequences of corruption are more difficult to quantify. It is generally accepted that growing perceptions of corruption diminish trust in public institutions (Susan, 2001).

Study Summary and Conclusion

It would be prudent to point from the study that corruption has a significant social effect though much economic effect. Some studies have been devoted to the relationship between corruption and project performance and indeed found it undermines the development of poor countries as it impacts the economy directly by reducing economic investments corruption has adverse effects on investment and economic growth.

These studies indicate that bureaucratic corruption is rife in Kenya in various forms, and their effect on governance is real. Kenya has moved from a passive to an active phase where public servants, in particular, do not wait to be approached and bribed, for example, but actively and boldly solicit individuals to offer bribes.

Due to Bureaucratic corruption on hard core service delivery it is often true that services start failing from a

composite mixture of reasons. These are compounded due to the fact that BC;

- i. Poses significant risks to construction and engineering companies themselves;
- ii. in procurement it seems to reduce the productivity of public investment, reduce the quality of existing infrastructure, and reduce the capital spending productivity;
- iii. Leads to misallocation of resources;
- iv. Triggers a drastic fall in both the quantity and quality of services;
- v. Creates inefficiencies in public expenditure by diverting resources and policy decisions; and
- vi. Is systemic and goes beyond individuals to the structural and institutional levels.

As a result of these, there is a link between bureaucratic corruption and service delivery in devolved units as many a people who would not reach higher echelons of corruption now find proximity to the devolved units hence poor service delivery especially in the infrastructure. The correlation portends a critical policy issues in African management today since devolved units were meant to bring about egalitarianism for quick localized development that centralization hindered.

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